

Assessment of the Moisture Availability Index: A Case Study in Mapalana, Low Country Wet Zone of Sri Lanka

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Abstract

The intensification of droughts and the uncertainty of moisture variability under rising temperatures and declining precipitation patterns have significantly affected vegetation worldwide. The Moisture Availability Index (MAI)—defined as the ratio between dependable rainfall derived from long-term precipitation records and potential evapotranspiration—serves as a useful tool to evaluate irrigation requirements and assess the sustainability of rain-fed agriculture. This study estimated MAI in Mapalana, situated in the Low Country Wet Zone (LCWZ) of Sri Lanka, using 32 years (1990–2022) of climatic data. Dependable rainfall was calculated using the probability method, while potential evapotranspiration was estimated via the Thornthwaite empirical formula. A crop coefficient of 1.2 for rice (*Oryza sativa*) was applied to estimate actual evapotranspiration. The results indicate that MAI was relatively high during 1990–1996, had declined moderately from 1997–2001, and remained consistently low from 2002–2019. A temporary increase had occurred in 2020, potentially linked to reduced anthropogenic activities during the COVID-19 pandemic. Overall, findings suggest that the Mapalana region is currently experiencing moisture deficit conditions, which may negatively impact sustainable rice cultivation and water resource management.

Keywords: *Dependable rainfall, Evapotranspiration, Irrigation, Low country wet zone, Mapalana, Moisture Availability Index*